

QUIZ**LAST NAME: BOSCO****FIRST NAME: MAWA****PROGRAM CODE: PHGH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did did not use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did did not use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: xx%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. Which of the following is not regarded as plagiarism?

- Presenting common knowledge ideas without citation¹**
- Paraphrasing another person's ideas without attribution.
- Using a free internet image without attribution
- Using a quotation without a citation

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fourth Edition (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 34-35.

2. Which of the following regions are written in following the correct capitalization rule in the middle of a sentence?
- equatorial Africa**²
 - southern Africa
 - gulf of Mexico
 - Central Europe
3. Which of the following is a good research question?
- How many students are pursuing public health at Euclid University?
 - How many children aged five years and below are malnourished in South Sudan?**³
 - How many children died during the South Sudan civil war of 2016?
 - How many people in South Sudan attended Christmas prayers last year?
4. Which statement is correct about the table of contents?
- Table of contents lists the pages that preceded it
 - The page number of the table of contents itself is listed
 - A single space is left between the title “contents” and the first listed item
 - Table of content should be included in all documents with chapters**⁴
5. Effective graphics in a research report should:

² Cleenewerck and Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, 46.

³ Linda Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation* (Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, 2019), 28.

⁴ Kate Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers* (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2018), 402.

- Be boxed regardless of the number of figures in a document
 - Include as much data as possible
 - Be Simple labeled rows and columns⁵**
 - Have multiple colors
6. Which of the following is false about a qualitative researcher?
- Influences the interpretation of qualitative data
 - A qualitative researcher is a research tool
 - Acknowledges his/her subjectivity
 - Makes conclusions based on their own perspectives⁶**
7. Which of the following is a feature of qualitative research?
- Involves manipulation of the natural environment
 - Meaning of a phenomena is derived from the researcher's perspective
 - Relies on data from a single source
 - Offers rich contextual details of the research process⁷**
8. According to the WHO style, which of the following is considered discriminatory?
- Older people
 - Geriatrics⁸**
 - Elderly patients

⁵ Turabian, Kate L., *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 91.

⁶ Linda Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation*, 150.

⁷ Linda Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, 144.

⁸ World Health Organization, *WHO Style Guide* (Geneva: World Health Organization, 2013), 55.

Youth adults

9. Which qualitative research paradigm assumes that reality is socially constructed?

Postpositivism

Pragmatism

Interpretivist⁹

Critical Theory

10. Which of the following punctuation marks introduces a series of short elements?

Semicolons

Colons¹⁰

Hyphen

Apostrophes

⁹ Linda Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, 148.

¹⁰ World Health Organization, *WHO Style Guide*, 48.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Bloomberg, Linda and Volpe, Marie. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation*. Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, 2019.

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.